

ENTREPRENEURIAL SKILLS AND COMPETENCIES REQUIRED OF BUSINESS EDUCATION GRADUATES FOR SUSTAINABLE ENTERPRISE OPERATION

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Abstract: *Many business enterprises have failed due to lack of requisite business management skills of the entrepreneurs; however, it is expected of business education graduates to be self-sufficient as a result of the training secured during course of study. Therefore, this study identified the various entrepreneurial skills and competencies needed by business education graduates for sustainable business management. The study adopted a survey research design. The study population represented all the business education lecturers and final year undergraduates of the two Ogun State government-owned universities; Tai Solarin University of Education and Olabisi Onabanjo University. Adopting purposive and convenience sampling techniques, a sample of 124 respondents was drawn from the population, made up of 24 lecturers and 100 undergraduates. A structured questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection. Data collected were analyzed using the mean and standard deviation, and T-test. Findings revealed that 15 managerial skills, 14 marketing skills, 14 accounting skills and 15 ICT skills were required for sustainable operation of an enterprise. The hypothesis revealed that there is no significant difference in the opinion of lecturers and undergraduates on entrepreneurial skills required for sustainable operation of an enterprise. The study subsequently recommended that curriculum of Business Education should be reviewed with a view to incorporate the skills identified in the study in order to guarantee the adequate training (and making) of business education graduates who are set to establish and run*

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sustainable enterprises towards self-reliant and job creation – rather than hunting for the limited white collar jobs.

Introduction

Business education is part of the total programme of education in Nigeria which prepares individuals for specialized occupation in business field, and provides general knowledge about business enterprise. Esene (2012) corroborated this by saying that business education is the education for and about enterprise or training business skills. According to Okoli (2010), business education provides the knowledge, skills, understanding and attitude needed to perform effectively in the business world. Obi & Otamiri (2010) noted that a well trained business educator can effectively be engaged in proprietorship of private enterprise. It could be seen from the foregoing that the discipline places more emphasis on producing entrepreneurs who will have the capacity of creating businesses for themselves and employ others in order to justify the philosophical foundation of the discipline as *education for self-reliance*.

Entrepreneurial and business skills acquisition for self-reliance towards effective and sustainable business enterprise operation is often the focus of business education programme. The success or otherwise of a business education programme especially at higher education level could be adjudged based on the level of entrepreneurial skills acquired by its beneficiaries, i.e. the

undergraduates and graduates. Entrepreneurship is the process of discovering business opportunities and combining resources in order to render products or services for profit. Adeyanju, Okusanya & Ajayi (2010) explained that entrepreneurship as the establishment of small enterprise; the generation of business idea or identification of a business opportunity and putting in place a business to take advantage of the idea or opportunity within an economy; the process of actions taken by a person to discover business opportunities and exploits them into gainful venture by accepting the risk associated with it.

Consequently, a business is defined as the production of goods or provision of services for the purpose of profit making; business enterprise is an organization where business activities take place in order to satisfy people's need; and the person who is responsible for all the actions in entrepreneurship is called entrepreneur, a person who discovers business opportunity and turns it into a profitable venture.

In the opinion of Onifade (2004), an entrepreneur is an individual who undertakes to supply a goods or service to the market for profit; the person who undertakes the risk of new enterprises, directs the human and material resources towards the attainment of his business objectives. In line with these submissions, the

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motive of an entrepreneur is to make profit from business enterprise or venture. Entrepreneurial skills are those activity skills that will enable an entrepreneur to manage his own enterprise; business skills, which an individual acquires to enable him function effectively in the turbulent business environment as an entrepreneur or aself employed (Folahan&Omoniyi, 2006).The return on investment made an entrepreneur depends largely on skills and knowledge use in running the business, and among the skills to be focused in this study include managerial skills, marketing skills, accounting skills, and information and communication technology skills.

Management is the art of getting things done through people. It is the process of harnessing the diverse resources (materials, finance, people and time) in a manner as to achieve what the organisation set to achieve. Therefore, managerial skills are needed for proper management functioning such as planning, organising, directing and controlling human and material resources for effective running of a business. The objective of an enterprise is either production of goods or provision of services which must be accessible to consumers through effective marketing (Etonyeaku, 2011).

Meanwhile, marketing skills are needed to get the business goods and services across to the consumer at the right time in order to maximise sales volume and achieve the profitability objective of the business. The sales volume and

revenue must be properly recorded and adequately accounted, hence the need for accounting skills. Ezeani (2008) recognised accounting as the process of expressing the economic activities of everyday life in money terms, so that we may estimate the costs of creating goods and services, make decisions about production on the basis of these estimates, compare the actual costs as they occur with the estimate originally made, and adjust the output and prices of goods and services accordingly. The coordinating efforts of communicating result with application of modern technology is also important, hence the need for information and communication technology (ICT) skills.

A lot of people engage in entrepreneurship process especially operation of business enterprise without acquiring much skills and competencies that will ensure success in such endeavour (Akpotowoh&Amahi, 2006). As a result of this attitude, failure followed instead of success andtheir failure is not because they do not have the necessary capital and machines to stay afloat, but because they lack the prerequisite skills needed to grow from a small position to a bigger one, and as well to remain in the business. The situation now is that most business education graduates make little or no attempt to establish small scale business of their own despite the abundant business opportunities in the country. Instead, they continue to besiege private establishments, and diverse public AND private offices in search of jobs that are either

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extremely few in supply or even non-existent. The question now is what are entrepreneurial skills needed by business education graduates for sustainable operation of a business enterprise vis-à-vis managerial, marketing, financial management/accounting and ICT skills?

Objectives of the Study

The general objective of the study is to find out the perception of lecturers and undergraduates on entrepreneurial skills required by prospective business education graduates for sustainable business operation. Specifically, the study seeks to:

- i. Determine the managerial skills required by business education graduates for sustainable business operation.
- ii. Determine the marketing skills required by business education graduates for sustainable business operation.
- iii. Determine the accounting skills required by business education graduates for sustainable business operation.
- iv. Determine the ICT skills required by business education graduates for sustainable business operation.

Research Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between the mean rating of business education lecturers and undergraduates in their opinion on entrepreneurial skills required by business

education graduates for sustainable business operation

Methodology

The study employed a survey research design involving the use of questionnaire, unstructured interview and secondary data. The study population comprised of all the business education lecturers and final year undergraduates of the two selected tertiary institutions within the study area viz.; Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijagun and Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ago Iwoye. Adopting purposive and convenience sampling techniques, a sample 124 respondents was selected from the total population - a composition of 24 lecturers and 100 undergraduates. A quota of 56 respondents was given to each of the two tertiary institutions; a composition of six lecturers and fifty final year undergraduates per tertiary institution. A total of 124 copies of structured questionnaire were self-administered directly to the respondents, and 100% response rate was achieved. Interviews were conducted on selected respondents. Secondary data were collected from prior studies and relevant publications. Data collected were analysed using mean, standard deviation and t-test.

Findings

Research Question One: What are the managerial skills required by business education graduates for effective business operation?

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Table 1: Mean Rating and Standard Deviation of Respondents' Opinion on Managerial Skills Required of Prospective Business Education Graduates

S/N	Managerial Skills Required of Prospective Business Education Graduates	Mean	Std. Dev	Remark
1	Generation of business ideas and opportunities in setting up business	3.47	0.80	Required
2	Setting up appropriate business goals	3.40	0.84	Required
3	Planning and coordination of business resources for goal attaining	3.47	0.56	Required
4	Implementation of plan for goal attainment	3.14	0.58	Required
5	Business decisions making skill	3.34	0.62	Required
6	Bringing in innovative ideas and changes in the business	3.56	0.95	Highly required
7	Maintaining human relations among staff	3.54	0.74	Highly required
8	Effective communication and delegation of duties	3.92	0.83	Highly required
9	Setting up appropriate business plans	3.23	0.68	Required
10	Determination and management of risks	3.52	0.50	Highly required
11	Creation, maintenance and sustenance of customers	3.65	0.48	Highly required
12	Supervision of employees at work	3.55	0.50	Highly required
13	Appraisal of employees' performance	3.03	0.54	Required
14	Recognition of employees need for growth and development	2.07	0.79	Moderately required
15	Evaluation of business performance through feedback mechanism	3.19	0.74	Required
	Grand Mean	3.57		Highly required

Data analysis presented in Table 1 above showed that 6 items on the managerial skills required of prospective business education graduates were rated “*Highly Required*” because their mean values fell within 3.50 – 4.49; 8 items were rated “*Required*” because their mean values fell within 2.50 – 3.49 while only items 14 is rated “*Moderately Required*” because its mean values fell within 1.50 – 2.49. Consequently, the grand mean for all items on managerial skills required by business education graduates is 3.57 which fell within the real limit of 3.50 – 4.49 of “*Highly*

Required”. It therefore means that all the 15 managerial skills were required by prospective business education graduates for effective management of business enterprise. The values of standard deviation between 0.48 and 0.95 showed that respondents were homogeneous in their responses on managerial skills required by business education graduates for effective business operation.

Research Question Two: What are the marketing skills required by business education graduates for effective business operation?

Table 2: Mean Rating and Standard Deviation of Respondents’ Opinion on Marketing Skills Required of Prospective Business Education Graduates

S/ N	Marketing Skills Required of Prospective Business Education Graduates	Mean	Std. Dev	Remark
1	Determination of market trend for a products	3.94	0.63	Highly required
2	Determination of customers’ need	3.11	0.48	Required
3	Utilization of advertising to communicate the existence of product to customers	3.52	0.92	Highly required
4	Utilization of sales promotion to get more customers and extend market	3.85	0.64	Highly required
5	Identification of competitors’ strength and weaknesses	3.34	0.74	Required
6	Appreciation of customers’ behaviour	3.02	0.93	Required
7	Utilization of e-marketing platform to promote product	3.08	0.96	Required
8	Tapping good marketing ideas from effective competitors	1.42	0.57	Not required
9	Development of effective distribution channel in transporting products.	3.21	0.79	Required

10	Setting up of appropriate and affordable prices for products or services	3.11	1.09	Required
11	Establishing a feedback mechanism on product or services	3.89	0.70	Required
12	Conducting a periodic follow up on customers' compliant	3.26	1.09	Required
13	Periodic rebranding and improvement of product quality	2.68	0.47	Required
14	Using incentives to retain customers	2.35	0.48	Moderately required
15	Utilization of social media to promote goods	3.42	0.50	Required
	Grand Mean	3.15		Required

Data analysis presented in Table 2 showed that 3 items on the marketing skills were rated “*Highly Required*” because their mean values fell within 3.50 – 4.49; 10 items were rated “*Required*” because their mean values fell within 2.50 – 3.49. While items 14 and 8 were rated “*Moderately Required*” and “*Not Required*” respectively. Thus, the grand mean for all items on marketing skills required by prospective business education graduates is 3.15 which fell within the real limit of 2.50 – 3.49 of “*Required*”. It therefore means

that all the 14 marketing skills were required by business education graduates for sustainable operation of business enterprise. The values of standard deviation between 0.47 and 1.09 showed that respondents were homogeneous in their responses on marketing skills required by business education graduates for effective business operation.

Research Question Three: What are the accounting skills required by business education graduates for effective business operation?

Table 3: Mean Rating and Standard Deviation of Respondents' Opinion on Accounting Skills Required of Prospective Business Education Graduates

S/N	Accounting Skills Required of Prospective Business Education Graduates	Mean \bar{X}	Std. Dev	Remark
1	Knowledge of using sources documents for preparation of account.	3.50	0.50	Highly required
2	Preparation of cashbook and prime book.	3.47	0.50	Required
3	Preparation of debtors and creditors ledgers.	3.48	0.62	Required
4	Knowledge of Keeping sales and purchase records.	3.13	0.95	Required
5	Knowledge of double entry principle and other accounting concepts	3.18	0.89	Required
6	Correction of errors made during preparation of account	2.92	0.94	Required
7	Ability to calculate depreciation	2.69	0.87	Required
8	Preparation of financial statements.	3.79	0.93	Highly required
9	Interpretation of financial statement	3.24	0.97	Required
10	Preparation of bank reconciliation statements.	2.96	0.48	Required
11	Preparation of payrolls and understanding various deductions.	3.15	0.73	Required
12	Determination of employee wages and benefits.	3.45	0.71	Required
13	Processing accounts payable and account receivables	2.96	0.86	Required
14	Knowledge of federal, state and local regulations, levies and taxes levied on business organizations.	3.19	0.97	Required
15	Knowledge of cost accounting	1.81	0.55	Moderately required
	Grand Mean	3.13		Required

Data analysis presented in Table 3 overleaf showed that 2 items on the accounting skills were rated “*Highly Required*” because their mean values fell within 3.50 – 4.49; 12 items were rated “*Required*” because their mean values fell within 2.50 – 3.49 while only item 15 is rated “*Moderately Required*” because its mean values fell within 1.50 – 2.49. Consequently, the grand mean for all items on accounting skills required by prospective business education graduates is 3.13 which fell within the real limit of 2.50 – 3.49 of “*Required*”. It therefore means that 14

accounting skills were required by prospective business education graduates for sustainable management of business enterprise. The values of standard deviation between 0.48 and 0.97 showed that respondents were homogeneous in their responses on accounting skills required by business education graduates for effective business operation.

Research Question Four: What are the ICT skills required by business education graduates for effective business operation?

Table 4: Mean Rating and Standard Deviation of Respondents’ Opinion on ICT Skills Required of Prospective Business Education Graduates

S/N	Information and Communication Technology Skills Required of Prospective Business Education Graduates	Mean \bar{X}	Std. Dev	Remark
1	Knowledge of computer operation	3.32	0.85	Required
2	Creation, saving and printing documents	3.22	0.68	Required
3	Create and operating a website	3.19	0.93	Required
4	Access the internet through the use of mobile phones/telephone	3.19	0.97	Required
5	Sending bulk messages to customers	2.94	0.99	Required
6	Knowledge of using social media to promote goods or services	3.00	0.85	Required
7	Produce and send text documents electronically	3.06	0.92	Required
8	Browse and download information from the internet	2.75	0.89	Required
9	Conference calls/video conferencing for staff meetings	1.98	0.62	Moderately required
10	Database and Microsoft Access for storage and administration of staff data	2.84	0.58	Required

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11	Microsoft Excel to manage the company’s budget	3.65	0.48	Highly required
12	Microsoft Excel to prepare staff pay slip	3.52	0.50	Highly required
13	Knowledge of online product marketing	2.81	0.65	Required
14	Use e-mail to send business information to customers	3.13	0.81	Required
15	Knowledge of internet banking for payment and money transfer	2.87	0.49	Required
	Grand Mean	3.26		Required

Data analysis presented in Table 4 overleaf showed that 2 items were rated “*Highly Required*” because their mean values fell within 3.50 – 4.49 and 10 items were rated “*Required*” because their mean values fell within 2.50 – 3.49, while only item 9 is rated “*Moderately Required*” because its mean value fell within 1.50 – 2.49. Hence, the grand mean for all items on ICT skills required by prospective business education graduates is 3.26 which fell within the real limit of 2.50 – 3.49 of “*Required*”. It therefore means that all the 15 ICT skills were required by prospective business education graduates for

sustainable operation of business enterprise. The values of standard deviation between 0.49 and 0.99 showed that respondents were homogeneous in their responses on ICT skills required by business education graduates for sustainable business operation.

Research Hypothesis: There is no significant difference between the mean rating of business education lecturers and students on entrepreneurial skills required by business education graduates for effective business operation in Ogun State.

Table 5: T-test Analysis of Mean Rating of Lecturers and Students on Entrepreneurial Skills Required by Prospective Business Education Graduates

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Dev	Df	T-value	Sig. (2-tailed)	Decision
Lecturers	24	56.8	3.57	122	0.14	0.89	NS
Students	100	56.9	2.94				

The result of data analysis in Table 5 above revealed T-value of 0.14 and a significance value

of 0.89. The computed significance value of 0.89 is greater than the alpha significance of 0.05 at

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which it is being tested. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant difference is hereby accepted and this means that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of lecturers and students on entrepreneurial skills required by business education graduates for sustainable operation of business enterprise.

Discussions

Findings of the research question 1 as shown in Table 1 revealed that all the 15 managerial skills are required for sustainable operation of a business enterprise by graduates of business education. This is because the grand mean of all items on managerial skills is 3.57 which is higher than the mean cut off point of 2.50 upon which the decision of required and not required is based. This finding is in consonance with that of Etonyeaku, Kanu, Ezeji&Chukuma, 2014, Igberaharha, 2013, and Ezeani, Ifeonyemetalu&Ezemoyih, 2012. Etonyeaku, Kanu, Ezeji&Chukuma (2014) found that 10 managerial skills are needed by secretarial education graduates for sustainability in Enugu State. Similarly, Ezeani, Ifeonyemetalu&Ezemoyih (2012) reported that 9 managerial skills are required by business education graduates for effective operation of business enterprise in Enugu State. Likewise, Igberaharha (2013) stated that managerial skills are needed by business education graduates for effective job performance in Delta State.

Findings of the research question 2 as shown in Table 2 revealed that marketing skills are required for sustainable operation of a business enterprise by graduates of business education. This is because the grand mean of all items on marketing skills is 3.15 which is higher than the mean cut off point of 2.50 upon which the decision of required and not required is based. This finding is in consonance with that of Etonyeaku, Kanu, Ezeji&Chukwuma (2014) and Ezeani, Ifeonyemetalu&Ezemoyih (2012) that more than nine marketing skills are required by business education graduates for sustainability and effective operation of business enterprise in Enugu State.

The study found in research question 3 that 14 accounting skills are required by business education graduates for effective operation of business enterprise in Ogun State because the result showed mean ratings between 2.69- 3.79 which are greater than the mean cut off point of 2.50 upon which decision is based. These findings revealed the importance of accounting competence in the management of business enterprise because it allows proper accountability, stewardship reporting and management of business finance for better result. This finding is in agreement with that of Etonyeaku, Kanu, Ezeji&Chukuma, (2014), Igberaharha (2013), and Ezeani, Ifeonyemetalu&Ezemoyih, (2012). Etonyeaku, Kanu, Ezeji&Chukuma (2014) found that 10 accounting skills are needed by secretarial

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education graduates for sustainability in Enugu State.

Similarly, Ezeani, Ifeonyemetalu&Ezemoyih, (2012) reported that 9 accounting skills are required by business education graduates for effective operation of business enterprise in Enugu State. While Igberaharha (2013) stated that accounting and management skills are needed by business education graduates for effective job performance in Delta State.

Research question 4 found that 14 ICT skills are required by business education graduates for effective operation of business enterprise in Ogun State because the result of data analysis as shown in Table 4 revealed mean ratings between 2.84 and 3.65 which are all greater than the mean cut off point of 2.50 upon which decision is based. This result affirmed that ICT skills and competencies are inevitable for running business enterprise in this technological era. An entrepreneur without ICT skills is likely to be pushed out of the market by competitors because most of its operation will be slow due to non application ICT resources. This finding is in agreement with the result of Etonyeaku, Kanu, Ezeji&Chukuma(2014) that ICT skills are needed by secretarial education graduates for sustainability in Enugu State.

The findings of hypothesis tested found that the opinion of lecturers and students on entrepreneurial skills required by business education graduates for business operation were not significantly different because the result

of analysis as shown in Table 5 showed significant value of 0.89 which is greater than the alpha value of 0.05. This finding is in consonance with that of Igberaharha (2013) who reported that there is no significant difference between the mean responses of Business Educators and graduates on the accounting and management skills needed by Business Education graduates for effective job performance in Delta State. Similarly, Etonyeaku, Kanu, Ezeji&Chukuma (2014) found that there was no significant difference in the mean rating of the responses of the lecturers and students on managerial, marketing and ICT skills required for self sustainability by secretariat education graduates.

Conclusion

This study was embarked upon to find out the entrepreneurial skills required by business education graduates for sustainable operation of business enterprise in Ogun State. It was deduced that managerial skills are required by prospective entrepreneur for effective and sustainable planning, control, directing and organising of business affairs; marketing skills are required for getting the products or services of the business to the consumers at the right time in order to satisfy their wants; accounting skills are required for proper keeping of financial records and stewardship reporting, while ICT skills are required to meet up with the technological demand of today's business environment in by using ICT technologies to promote products and services. It was concluded

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that business education undergraduates who possess these entrepreneurial skills will effectively and efficiently operate a business enterprise in any part of the country.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn, the researchers outlined the following recommendations:

- i. There is the need to strengthen the impartation of basic entrepreneurial skills in the implementation of entrepreneurship studies in institutions of higher learning so that graduates will possess the required skills.
- ii. Business education curriculum should be reviewed with a view to incorporate the skills identified in this study in order to ensure the training and making of business education graduates who are ready to establish business outfit for self sufficiency and job creation.
- iii. There is the need for both undergraduates and graduates of business education to strive towards the acquisition of basic entrepreneurial skills outlined in this study, and be ready to put them into use towards achieving self sustenance in business operations.
- iv. Periodic training and retraining programmes should be put in place for business educators to update their knowledge and skills on modern entrepreneurial skills required by students to ensure effective teaching of small businesses and entrepreneurship studies in business education programmes.

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